

Flood vulnerability assessment: a methodological approach applied in Colindres (Cantabria)

V.M. Bruschi; J. Weichselgartner; J. Bertens; J. Remondo; A. González Díez

Introduction

With the UN conferences on environment and development (Rio de Janeiro 1992) and natural disaster reduction (Yokohama 1994) it became clear that disaster management must become part of sustainable development strategies (German IDNDR Committee, 1999). The relevance of natural hazards has also been pointed out in Europe (EEA, 1998). Hazards affect spaces settled by people, which underlay specific social, political, economic as well as historical conditions and circumstances. However, natural science literature frequently ignores the socially constructed and culturally contextualized nature of natural hazards. Usually emphasis is placed on analysis of physical processes (hazard) and human infrastructure (exposure) but limited concern is devoted to social components (vulnerability) (Fig. 1). Furthermore, there is limited knowledge transfer

and information interchange between science and local authorities, communities, and decision-makers in environmental and mitigation policies. As a consequence, hazard and environmental policy is less control than reaction; it follows

Fig. 1: Relationship between geomorphological environment and man

correcting and compensating an independent social dynamics. The approach proposed here is applied to an area in the Spanish municipality of Colindres (Fig. 2). The economy of the area is based on fishing, manufacturing industry, and summer tourism; a nature reserve occupies part of the study site. The most relevant and frequent hazard in the study area are floods. Therefore, objectives, measures, and policy actions concern this type of hazard.

Fig. 2: Study site in Colindres, Cantabria (Spain)

Poster illustrates an approach towards sustainable environmental policy-making in natural risk and disaster management.

Fig. 3 portrays the proposed synthesis of physical and social components in risk assessment. Fig. 4a illustrates the integration in disaster management. Fig. 4b graphically shows the methodological scheme presented in Fig. 4a and its application in practice.

Fig. 3: Natural risk assessment process

Fig. 4a: Natural disaster management process

Initially natural hazard (Box I), exposure, preparedness (Box II), prevention (Box III), and response (Box IV) characteristics are analysed and assessed. Vulnerability (Box V) is introduced to take into account the condition of a given area and the ability of its set of elements to cope with events of a certain physical character.

Fig. 4b: Application of approach.

The analysed variables are highly changeable. Therefore, a constant evaluation of these factors, best described as *Vulnerability Index* (Comfort et al., 1999), is essential. As a last step modifications and measures need to be analysed and assessed continuously. This forms the input for renewed analysis and assessment (risk management).

<p>Natural Hazard Analysis Box I</p> <p>Objectives: Identification, inventory, and assessment of all natural events in a given area which can potentially damage human life and property. Measures: Analysis of physical processes</p>	<p>Preparedness Analysis Box II</p> <p>Objectives: Identification, inventory, and assessment of precautionary activities and measures in a given area to be prepared best of natural disaster. Measures: Analysis of awareness warning, evacuation, and disaster relief variables.</p>	<p>Prevention Analysis Box III</p> <p>Objectives: Identification, inventory, and assessment of all activities and measures in a given area to prevent hazards and their effects and provide permanent protection from their impacts. Measures: Analysis of structural and non-structural measures.</p>	<p>Response Analysis Box IV</p> <p>Objectives: Identification, inventory, and assessment of all response activities and measures in a given area to reduce social and economic damage and losses. Measures: Analysis of search, rescue, humanitarian assistance, recovery, and reconstruction structures.</p>	<p>Vulnerability Analysis Box V</p> <p>Objectives: Assessment of the existing condition of a given area and its ability to cope and respond to specific natural hazard events and their impacts. Measures: Analysis of hazards characteristics, socio-economic, exposure, preparedness, prevention, and response variables.</p>
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The approach demonstrates both need and possibility to synthesise physical as well as social factors in natural risk assessment and disaster management. Natural disasters are rather the result of a cumulative set of social decisions taken over long periods in a number of fields than the result of physical hazard characteristics. They serve as evidence of the need for changes in public policy and practice. Consequently, the process by which these choices are made become a focal point for potential change and sustainable development. The approach considers disaster management practice and policy as a comprehensive and continuous activity; not as a periodic reaction to individual disaster circumstances. However, listing the solutions is simple; it is the implementation that brings the problems.

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 FODISPIL - Aplicación de la fotografía digital al análisis de la susceptibilidad y peligrosidad de los procesos de inestabilidad de laderas (Contract No. REN 2002-00076).

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